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Rethinking Classroom Power and Knowledge: A Foucauldian Analysis

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Abstract

The study examines how power is exercised and perceived in educational contexts, especially in classroom settings, in the light of Michel Foucault's theory of power. Transcending the traditional hierarchical view of classroom power, the research explores how authority and control circulate in the pedagogic environment. The study focuses more on understanding the power dynamics between teacher-student interactions. Employing a random sampling technique, the data is collected from 40 participants from different schools, colleges and universities of Dera Ghazi Khan. The data is collected with a quantitative research method using a pre-structured questionnaire consisting of 20 items. The collected data is analysed using IBM SPSS Statistics 20; frequency-based descriptive analysis is conducted to understand how participants view the concepts of power, authority and control in a classroom environment. The sample is taken from 40 participants, and the reliability coefficient of Cronbach's alpha is 0.867. The purpose of the study is to analyse whether Foucauldian notions of power are consistent with the classroom realities. The study contributes to the scholarly discourses by providing practical evidence of how power is perceived in educational environments. The findings of the study reveal that various power structures suggested by Michel Foucault can be seen in educational settings, especially his bottom-up approach to power and his idea of power as a circulating force, and can be found everywhere.

Keywords: classroom-authority, education, institutions, power

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1. Introduction

Education is a useful component in the development, modification, and construction of the social system, while power is an intrinsic and inescapable element of the pedagogic environment. It affects classroom interaction, and it also helps strategic planning within educational institutions. In a traditional classroom setting, teachers hold the authority and control over students, whereas students play passive roles. This demonstrates a hierarchical learning space. However, Michel Foucault disagrees with this idea; he believes that power is always moving and changing. The idea of power, directed by Foucault's thoughts, sees power not as a possession but as a moving force that can be seen in ordinary relationships and everyday interactions. Michel Foucault exclaims that power is practised through discourse (Foucault, 1980). In educational settings, teachers and students both take part in negotiating and constructing power. Following the specific rules, sharing knowledge, communicating ideas, and assessment practices explain that power works in a learning space. Teachers have power given by the institute, whereas students may showcase agency by obeying, resisting or cooperating. Hence, a classroom is a place where power is always being shared, and the learning atmosphere demonstrates a complex exchange of authority, arbitration and supremacy rather than a traditional hierarchical space.

1.1 Research Questions

The research questions of the study are as follows

1. What is the frequency of power perceived and experienced in the classroom environment?
2. What are the reported levels of power as reflected in relational and dynamic aspects of a classroom environment?
3. What are the measured levels of institutional practices and power-knowledge relations shaping the behaviours in learning spaces?

1.2 Research Objectives

The research objectives of the study are as follows

1. To explore the frequency of power perceived and experienced in the classroom

environment.

2. To understand the reported levels of power as reflected in a relational and dynamic classroom environment
3. To examine the measured levels of institutional practices and power-knowledge relation shaping the behaviours in learning spaces

1.3 Delimitations

The responses obtained in this study are limited to 40 participants. The participants involved in this study are only residents of Dera Ghazi Khan City. The theoretical framework of the study is delimited to Michel Foucault, particularly his theory of power and knowledge. The study uses a questionnaire-based quantitative design to collect data. Interviews and other qualitative data collection methods are beyond the scope of this research. Moreover, the questionnaire contains no items directly addressing discourse, language, or communicative practices in classrooms, as classroom power is largely discursive in the form of teacher questions, praise, criticism, topic selection, and turn-taking norms.

1.4 Ethical Consideration

Ethical guidelines are being followed, and verbal consent has been taken from participants and the heads of the institutes, which is also acceptable in the process of research. The anonymised data do not make the names of the participants compulsory while filling google form.

2. Literature Review

The research focuses on Foucauldian studies of classroom power by presenting that power is a tool used for social reproduction and domination in a traditional classroom setting. "Hence, teachers can be regarded as agents of bureaucratic hegemony, for good or for ill, in any society" (Victor, Moeketsi, 2013). The study examines how power is negotiated in a classroom. In a traditional classroom, power was used as a tool for domination, while in the modern education system, teachers use power to manage the classroom rather than to demonstrate control and authority, which is

seen as an improvement according to the authors.

Adding on empirical applications of power-knowledge in educational settings, Allen Rose, in his work, studies the competing discourses in pedagogy and their link with power dynamics among teachers, administrators and technologies within modern education systems. The author also focuses on how a teacher should control or teach the class by using Michel Foucault's philosophy of power. Rose argues, "Both technology and public policy discourses have the effect of diverting attention away from dislocating traditional teaching practices" (Rose, 2022). However, this research is limited to a single school setting and its overemphasis on the teacher's role only. The research doesn't highlight the impact of competing educational discourses on students, indicating a gap that future researchers could address.

Further, teacher-student power negotiations are depicted by Ayhan and Riza, highlighting the relation of teachers' educational beliefs with their understanding of education, teaching and ideology. The main argument of the study is that power and knowledge are linked, and the capability of teachers depends on their knowledge, which also determines their power. In educational practices, power and knowledge highly influence how teachers shape their professional identities and classroom functions. Aksakalli and Salar argue, "Power uses schools as a fundamental tool to impose its presence and influence on teachers" (Ayhan, Riza, 2023). In general, the study explains how the power-knowledge relations construct educational beliefs. Similarly, Danielsson, Berge and Lidar, in their work, explore the constitution of power and knowledge in classroom settings and study their relationship with teacher-student interaction, primarily in technology classes. The authors explain that "educational content needs to be understood as integral to the execution of power in the classroom" (Anna, Maria, Malena, 2017). Expanding on this, Moscovici, in one of his articles, exclaims that power in pedagogic spaces is exercised through various institutional and

interpersonal mediums that highly influence teaching behaviours. He argues, "teaching and exploring power relationships in science teachers' lives is essential if we want the teachers to change their practices toward inquiry science" (Hedy, 2003). He examines teachers' experiences of operating authority in the absence of formal training or certification.

By critically reviewing the existing literature, the previous studies have contributed thoroughly to examining classroom power and how it is widely influenced by institutional structures, educational discourses, and professional identities. The existing literature significantly supports Michel Foucault's concept of power. Scholars, including Pitsoe and Letseka, suggest that classroom power has now shifted from mere control to a more regulative form, where students also participate in maintaining classroom order. Similarly, Patrick Allen Rose further explains this discussion by explaining how competing institutional and technological discourses reshape teachers' authority and legitimise particular educational content within classrooms. While Aksakalli and Salar argue that teachers' professional identity is not independent but rather constructed through organisational ideologies. The power and knowledge relation is further studied by Anna T. Danielsson and her colleagues; they illustrate that a certain type of knowledge is given preference by higher management in educational settings, which blocks teachers' individual pedagogic decisions in classrooms. Moscovici's ideas also analyse the role of institutional hierarchies in shaping teacher roles and classroom powers. However, various limitations are clearly seen in their fragmented focus on either teachers or organisational forces, often missing out on students' perceptions of power relations in educational contexts. The gap outlines a need to examine how both groups perceive and experience power in everyday educational engagements. The research provides a more comprehensive awareness of how power is produced in classroom interactions.

3. Theoretical Framework

Michel Foucault's main ideas on power are: power is not owned or possessed by a specific entity; rather, it is a moving force that circulates in society. (Foucault, 1980). It is not limited to rulers or policymakers but can be found everywhere. Power operates through normal interactions and everyday practices. "Knowledge and power are integrated, and there is no point in dreaming of a time when knowledge will cease to depend on power; power can't be exercised without knowledge; it is impossible for knowledge not to engender power" (Foucault, 1980, p. 52).

Moreover, Foucault says that politicians and rulers build their discourse in the public minds to exercise their power. He says that power uses knowledge and language to shape what people think. Shared beliefs are spread through strong discourses, which result in individuals controlling themselves accordingly and participating in power dynamics: "Wherever there is power, there is resistance" (Michel, 1978, p. 95). Foucault believes that power works from bottom to top as well. Power is not something that is used on people; rather, it works through people, "He says that his objective is to create a history of the different modes in which, in our culture, human beings are made subjects" (Panneerselvam, 2000). Michel Foucault has also explored all the types of power he saw in society and around him.

Dominant systems and several organisations, like schools, lawmakers, and prisons, are used to mentor people so they act in a specific way without using direct force on them, working as a power-knowledge nexus in the education system. Foucault has used the concept of Bentham's Panopticon, a prison design where prisoners are always being watched. (Michel, 2008, p. 24). Higher authorities or the government use this power to keep the public healthy, productive and under control. "Biopower is achieved through the production of scientific knowledge, including information about health and fitness, which constructs ideas of the normal body" (Raine, S., 2023). Foucault emphasises that power and knowledge often come together. They are linked,

and the presence of knowledge results in the production of power. If you have knowledge, it gives you power, as knowledge is used to influence people, and power helps in authenticating that knowledge, "Knowledge and power are integrated, and there is no point in dreaming of a time when knowledge will cease to depend on power; power can't be exercised without knowledge; it is impossible for knowledge not to engender power" (Foucault, 1980, p. 52).

4. Research Methodology

The study adopted a quantitative research design to collect data from 40 participants, using a predesigned questionnaire having 20 items related to the public perspective on Foucault's theory of power and knowledge. The random sampling technique was adopted to collect responses from the students and teachers from various schools, colleges and universities of Dera Ghazi Khan, which helped in gathering the perspectives of wider contexts and populations from all over the area via Google Form. The measurement of perceptions quantitatively enhances the complexity of power as it acknowledges that power is both relational and discursive, like Michel Foucault's concept of power. Power is not just possessed, but it is also experienced and internalised, and a quantitative approach can capture this internalisation at scale by making invisible dynamics more visible through quantitative data.

The study took a duration of 5 months from [September 2025](#) to [January 2026](#), and during 5 months, the following actions were performed: inception of the idea, literature review, devising of the questionnaire, dissemination of the Google Form and analysis on SPSS. The 1st draft of the research and its evaluation from the teacher and experts, and the incorporation of revisions were done after 5 months, which was the write-up stage of the actual research. The manuscript treats this location as merely a geographic boundary rather than a meaningful cultural context that shapes how power is perceived and exercised. Pakistani classroom dynamics differ substantially from Western

contexts where most Foucaultian educational research has been conducted. IBM SPSS Statistics 20 was used for frequency analysis findings were interpreted through descriptive analysis using tables to demonstrate the results. To authenticate the internal reliability of research evaluation tools, a reliability test was conducted using Cronbach's Alpha. The consistency analysis of this research shows a Cronbach's Alpha value of 0.867, which highlights strong reliability. Thus, the research tools used in this research can be considered authentic and reliable for analysing the perspectives of power in academic settings.

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.867	20

5. Analysis

In this part, the findings are analysed and discussed using frequency tables. The tables show respondents' responses recorded on a 5-point Likert scale as: 1= Strongly Agree, 2= Agree, 3= Neutral, 4=Disagree, 5=Strongly Disagree. The questionnaire was designed in alignment with the research objectives in order to establish coherence and analytical clarity. The first objective, which observes the perceptions of power and control within a classroom, is addressed through questions 1, 10, 11 and 12, focusing on how power works in everyday classroom interactions. The second objective, which seeks to understand the perspectives of teachers and students on the Foucauldian concept of power as a dynamic and relational force, is addressed through questions 2, 13, 14, 15, and 16. The third objective, which explores the influence of institutional power and power-knowledge relations, is addressed through questions 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 17, 18, 19 and 20.

Table No. 5.1: Power is not limited to governments or rulers but exists in everyday life.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	13	32.5	32.5	32.5
	2	21	52.5	52.5	85.0
	3	4	10.0	10.0	95.0
	4	2	5.0	5.0	100.0
	Total	40	100.0	100.0	

Table 5.1 shows respondents' views on the statement that power is not limited to government or rulers but exists in everyday life. The responses indicate that 32.5% of respondents strongly agree and 52.5% of respondents agree with the statement, while 10.0% of respondents stay neutral and 5.0% of respondents disagree with the statement. The majority of the responses (85%) agree with the idea that power is diffused; it is not owned solely by the government or any group. On the other hand, only a small number of responses (15%) stay neutral or disagree with this idea. Hence, the results show that the majority of responses support Foucault's idea and prove that his theory is practical and based on real-life experience.

Table No. 5.2: According to Foucault, power is not something that people 'possess' but something that operates in relationships.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	5	12.5	12.5	12.5
	2	27	67.5	67.5	80.0
	3	5	12.5	12.5	92.5
	4	3	7.5	7.5	100.0
	Total	40	100.0	100.0	

Table 5.2 shows respondents' views on the statement that, according to Foucault, power is not something that people possess but something that operates in relationships. The responses indicate that 12.5% of respondents strongly agree and a strong amount of 67.5% of respondents agree with the statement, while 12.5% of respondents stay neutral and 7.5% of respondents disagree with the statement. The majority of the responses (80%) support the idea that power is not owned by people; it is exercised through people. On the other hand, only a small number of responses (20%) stay neutral or disagree with this idea. Hence, the results show that the majority of responses support Foucault's idea and prove that his thoughts on power and how it is being used in society are based on real-life examples.

Table No. 5.3: Power is everywhere because it arises from all social interactions.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	7	17.5	17.5	17.5
	2	32	80.0	80.0	97.5
	3	1	2.5	2.5	100.0
	Total	40	100.0	100.0	

Table 5.3 reveals respondents' views on the statement that power is everywhere because it arises from all social interactions. The responses indicate that 17.5% of respondents strongly agree and 80.0% of respondents agree with the statement, while 2.5% of respondents stay neutral, and no one disagrees with the statement. A large portion of the responses (97.5%) agree with the idea that power is diffused; it is present everywhere, including social groups, higher organisations, and everyday interactions. On the other hand, only a small number of responses (2.5%) remain neutral with this idea. Hence, the results show that the majority of responses support Foucault's idea and prove that his theory is practical and based on real-life experience.

Table No. 5.4: Institutions like schools, hospitals, and prisons are key sites where power operates.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	5	12.5	12.5	12.5
	2	27	67.5	67.5	80.0
	3	6	15.0	15.0	95.0
	5	2	5.0	5.0	100.0
	Total	40	100.0	100.0	

Table 5.4 shows respondents' views on the statement that institutions like schools, hospitals, and prisons are key sites where power operates. The responses indicate that 12.5% of respondents strongly agree and 67.5% of respondents agree with the statement, while 15.0% of respondents stay neutral and 5.0% of respondents strongly disagree with the statement. Even though the majority of the responses (80%) agree with the idea that power is exercised through a few institutions, a small number of responses (5.0%) strongly disagree with this idea. This ratio of strong disagreement shows few different experiences, but the majority of responses support Foucault's concept that certain institutions play an important role in operating

power in society.

Table No. 5.5: Power is not only repressive but also productive, shaping knowledge and truth.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	10	25.0	25.0	25.0
	2	20	50.0	50.0	75.0
	3	7	17.5	17.5	92.5
	4	3	7.5	7.5	100.0
	Total	40	100.0	100.0	

Table 5.5 shows respondents' views on the statement that power is not only repressive but also productive, shaping knowledge and truth. The responses reveal that 25.0% of respondents strongly agree and a strong amount of 50.0% of respondents agree with the statement, while 17.5% of respondents stay neutral, and 7.5% of respondents disagree with the statement. The majority of the responses (75%) support the idea that power is not owned by people; it is exercised through people. On the other hand, only a small number of responses (25%) stay neutral or disagree with this idea. Hence, the results show that the majority of the students and teachers do not see power as a repressive force and believe that power is productive and necessary to shape behaviours and knowledge. The majority supports Foucault's perspective of power and believes that power plays a part in shaping knowledge and shared truths.

Table No. 5.6: Knowledge and power are inseparable; knowledge helps sustain power.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	8	20.0	20.0	20.0
	2	26	65.0	65.0	85.0
	3	5	12.5	12.5	97.5
	5	1	2.5	2.5	100.0
	Total	40	100.0	100.0	

Table 5.6 reveals respondents' views on the statement that knowledge and power are inseparable; knowledge helps sustain power. The findings indicate that 20.0% of respondents strongly agree and 65.0% of respondents agree with the statement, while 12.5% of respondents stay neutral and 2.5% of respondents strongly disagree with the statement. Even though the

majority of the responses (85.0%) agree with the idea that power and knowledge are correlated, a small number of responses (2.5%) strongly disagree with this idea. This ratio of strong disagreement shows few different perspectives; a few may think that sometimes those having power do not have knowledge, but the majority of responses support Foucault's concept that power and knowledge come together, and knowledge helps in sustaining power.

Table No. 5.7: Disciplines such as medicine, psychology, and law exercise power by defining 'truth'.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	4	10.0	10.0	10.0
	2	24	60.0	60.0	70.0
	3	10	25.0	25.0	95.0
	4	1	2.5	2.5	97.5
	5	1	2.5	2.5	100.0
	Total	40	100.0	100.0	

Table 5.7 reveals varied responses to the statement that disciplines such as medicine, psychology, and law exercise power by defining 'truth'. The responses reveal that 10.0% of respondents strongly agree and 60.0% of respondents agree with the statement, while 25.0% of respondents stay neutral, 2.5% of respondents disagree, and 2.5% of respondents strongly disagree with the statement. Even though the majority of the responses (70.0%) either agree or strongly agree with the idea that power is exercised through major institutes or disciplines, including law, medicine and psychology, a small number of responses (5%) show disagreement or strong disagreement with this idea. While a few shows lack understanding of this idea and choose to stay neutral. Overall, the majority of responses support Foucault's concept that power is being exercised through shared truths.

Table No. 5.8: What society accepts as 'truth' is influenced by those who hold power.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	12	30.0	30.0	30.0
	2	23	57.5	57.5	87.5

	3	2	5.0	5.0	92.5
	4	3	7.5	7.5	100.0
	Total	40	100.0	100.0	

Table 5.8 shows responses to the statement that what society accepts as 'truth' is influenced by those who hold power. The findings indicate that 30.0% of respondents strongly agree and 57.5% of respondents agree with the statement, while 5.0% of respondents stay neutral and 7.5% of respondents disagree with the statement. The majority of the respondents (87.5%) either agree or strongly agree with the idea that power shapes our societal beliefs and our shared truths. Hence, the findings provide strong support in favour of Foucault's ideas.

Table No. 5.9: Surveillance (e.g., CCTV, monitoring in schools/workplaces) is a form of power that produces discipline.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	7	17.5	17.5	17.5
	2	24	60.0	60.0	77.5
	3	7	17.5	17.5	95.0
	4	2	5.0	5.0	100.0
	Total	40	100.0	100.0	

Table 5.9 shows responses to the statement that surveillance (e.g., CCTV, monitoring in schools/workplaces) is a form of power that produces discipline. The 17.5% of respondents strongly agree, and 60.0% of respondents agree with the statement, while 17.5% of respondents stay neutral, and 5.0% of respondents disagree with the statement. The majority of the respondents (77.5%) either agree or strongly agree with the idea that powerful authorities use surveillance to monitor people's behaviours and to keep them disciplined. Hence, the findings reveal strong support in favour of Foucault's ideas.

Table No. 5.10: Foucault's concept of power/knowledge helps explain how academic systems control students.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	6	15.0	15.0	15.0
	2	24	60.0	60.0	75.0

	3	8	20.0	20.0	95.0
	4	2	5.0	5.0	100.0
	Total	40	100.0	100.0	

Table 5.10 shows responses to the statement that Foucault's concept of power/knowledge helps explain how academic systems control students. The findings show that 15.0% of respondents strongly agree and 60.0% of respondents agree with the statement, while 20.0% of respondents stay neutral and 5.0% of respondents disagree with the statement. Thus, the majorities of the respondents (75.0%) either agree or strongly agree with the idea that Foucault's ideas help us in understanding how the educational system controls students through power. Hence, the findings support Foucault's ideas.

Table No. 5.11: Power operates at the micro-level of daily life, not just at the state or government level.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	11	27.5	27.5	27.5
	2	27	67.5	67.5	95.0
	3	2	5.0	5.0	100.0
	Total	40	100.0	100.0	

Table 5.11 shows responses to the statement that power operates at the micro-level of daily life, not just at the state or government level. Among all the responses, 27.5% of respondents strongly agree, and 67.5% of respondents agree with the statement, while 5.0% of respondents stay neutral with the statement. Thus, the high ratio of the respondents (95.0%) either agree or strongly agree with the idea of micro power and believe that power is everywhere. It operates at a micro level and is not bound to macro-political structures. The responses were taken from both the teachers and students, and a large ratio of responses are in support of the existence of micro power, which suggests that students also feel power within an educational context. Overall, findings are in favour of the Foucauldian idea that everyone holds power in society and power exists at the micro level as well.

Table No. 5.12: Teachers, parents, and supervisors exercise forms of power similar to

those of the institution.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	5	12.5	12.5	12.5
	2	27	67.5	67.5	80.0
	3	7	17.5	17.5	97.5
	4	1	2.5	2.5	100.0
	Total	40	100.0	100.0	

Table 5.12 shows responses to the statement that teachers, parents, and supervisors exercise forms of power similar to institutions. The findings show that 12.5% of respondents strongly agree and 67.5% of respondents agree with the statement, while 17.5% of respondents stay neutral, and 2.5% of respondents disagree with the statement. Thus, the high ratio of the responses (80%) shows their support for the idea of teachers and parents holding similar power as institutions.

Table No. 5.13: Everyday rules (such as dress codes, attendance, and punctuality) are examples of disciplinary power.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	8	20.0	20.0	20.0
	2	26	65.0	65.0	85.0
	3	2	5.0	5.0	90.0
	4	4	10.0	10.0	100.0
	Total	40	100.0	100.0	

Table 5.13 shows responses to the statement that everyday rules (such as dress codes, attendance, and punctuality) are examples of disciplinary power. The responses reveal that 20.0% of respondents strongly agree and 65.0% of respondents agree with the statement, while 5.0% of respondents stay neutral, and 10.0% of respondents disagree with the statement. Thus, the high ratio of the responses (85%) shows their support for the idea that dress codes, punctuality and attendance are examples of disciplinary power.

Table No. 5.14: Resistance to authority is also a part of power relations.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	8	20.0	20.0	20.0

	2	27	67.5	67.5	87.5
	3	4	10.0	10.0	97.5
	4	1	2.5	2.5	100.0
	Total	40	100.0	100.0	

Table 5.14 shows responses to the statement that resistance to authority is also a part of power relations. The results show that 20.0% of respondents strongly agree and 67.5% of respondents agree with the statement, while 10.0% of respondents stay neutral, and 2.5% of respondents disagree with the statement. Thus, the high ratio of the responses (87.5%) supports the idea that resistance is also part of the power relations.

Table No. 5.15: Power is dynamic and can shift depending on social interactions.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	8	20.0	20.0	20.0
	2	25	62.5	62.5	82.5
	3	4	10.0	10.0	92.5
	4	2	5.0	5.0	97.5
	5	1	2.5	2.5	100.0
	Total	40	100.0	100.0	

Table 5.15 demonstrates varied responses to the statement that power is dynamic and can shift depending on social interactions. The results indicate that 20.0% of respondents strongly agree and 62.5% of respondents agree with the statement, while 10.0% of respondents stay neutral, 5.0% of respondents disagree, and 2.5% of respondents strongly disagree with the statement. But the high ratio of the responses (82.5%) supports the idea that power is dynamic in nature; it is not fixed and can shift according to social interactions.

Table No. 5.16: Where there is power, there is always a possibility of resistance.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	11	27.5	27.5	27.5
	2	23	57.5	57.5	85.0
	3	6	15.0	15.0	100.0
	Total	40	100.0	100.0	

Table 5.16 shows responses to the statement that where there is power, there is always a

possibility of resistance. The results show that 27.5% of respondents strongly agree and 57.5% of respondents agree with the statement, while 15.0% of respondents stay neutral with the statement. But the high ratio of the responses (85%) supports the idea that power produces resistance. Power can't exist without resistance.

Table No. 5.17: Resistance is not outside power but exists within it.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	10	25.0	25.0	25.0
	2	22	55.0	55.0	80.0
	3	7	17.5	17.5	97.5
	4	1	2.5	2.5	100.0
	Total	40	100.0	100.0	

Table 5.17 shows that 25.0% of respondents strongly agree and 55.0% of respondents, among the 40 participants of the study, agree with Foucauldian philosophy, while 17.5% of respondents stay neutral and 2.5% of respondents disagree with the statement. Overall, the high ratio of responses (80%) indicates that resistance emerges from inside the power instead of existing solely.

Table No. 5.18: Social movements (e.g., feminism, environmentalism, human rights) can be understood as forms of resistance to power.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	10	25.0	25.0	25.0
	2	20	50.0	50.0	75.0
	3	8	20.0	20.0	95.0
	4	2	5.0	5.0	100.0
	Total	40	100.0	100.0	

Table 5.18 shows that 25.0% of respondents strongly agree and 50.0% of respondents, among the 40 respondents, agree that feminism, human rights and other social movements are the type of resistance against power structures, while 20.0% of respondents stay neutral and 5.0% of respondents disagree with the statement. Overall, the high ratio of responses (75%) indicates that social movements are collective actions that emerged as a result of excessive use of power.

Table No. 5.19: Understanding Foucault's concept of power can help students critically analyse social structures.

		Frequency	Percentage	Valid Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
Valid	1	9	22.5	22.5	22.5
	2	20	50.0	50.0	72.5
	3	11	27.5	27.5	100.0
	Total	40	100.0	100.0	

Table 5.19 demonstrates that 72.5% of respondents either strongly agree or agree that students need to study Foucauldian theories to understand social structures and power relations in society. While 27.5% of respondents stay neutral and show their lack of clear understanding regarding it. Overall, findings reveal public awareness of the importance of Foucauldian philosophy to understand power relations and social structures in society.

Table No. 5.20: Foucault's theory of power is relevant for understanding contemporary issues (e.g., media influence, surveillance, politics).

		Frequency	Percentage	Valid Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
Valid	1	4	10.0	10.0	10.0
	2	27	67.5	67.5	77.5
	3	7	17.5	17.5	95.0
	4	1	2.5	2.5	97.5
	5	1	2.5	2.5	100.0
	Total	40	100.0	100.0	

Table 5.20 shows respondents' views on the statement that Foucault's theory of power is relevant for understanding contemporary issues (e.g., media influence, surveillance, politics). A total of 40 responses were collected, among which 77.5% of respondents either agree or strongly agree with the statement, while a few remain neutral or disagree with it. But the overwhelming ratio of respondents believes that Foucauldian theory can be applicable to contemporary issues and can help us in understanding the power dynamics and power structures within contemporary society.

6. Discussion

Among most of the items, collective agreement ranged from 70% to 97.5%, combining strongly agree and agree. As Tables 5.3 and 5.11

shows 97.5% and 90% agreement that power is everywhere and operates at the micro level. These patterns imply that the sample highly support fundamental ideas of Foucault incorporating diffuseness of power as in table 5.1 with 85% agreement, relational nature of power in table 5.2 with 80% agreement, and institutional power in table 5.4 with 80% agreement also, role of surveillance in disciplinary power (table 5.9 with 77% agreement) further suggests that respondents are aware of daily regulation and role of academic systems to influence behaviors. Moreover, an analytical attention is required for the few responses (generally 5-20%) that strongly disagree, disagree or stayed neutral as showed in table 5.4 (5%) strongly disagreed with the idea of institutional power, also in table 5.7 where 5% of the respondents shows disagreement or strong disagreement with the idea that medicines, law and other disciplines define truth and play a role in operating power in society. While the difference in responses is in the minority, yet indicate the different understandings of power. There is a need to conduct future research to examine this small number of opposing voices that believe in the single authority holders and view power as an entirely repressive force.

These descriptive patterns show that the experience of this sample in Dera Ghazi Khan aligns with Foucault's framework. Teachers and students both do not view classroom power as a purely top-down or oppressive force, as seen by high acceptance of micro power, disciplinary norms and productive nature of power. Rather, they believe that knowledge, norms and interactions between relationships are the main medium of power circulation. In general, this descriptive study offers initial, but not definitive, evidence that Foucauldian notions are applicable in this context.

7. Conclusion

The purpose of this study was to use Foucault's theoretical framework to investigate how power, authority, resistance and knowledge are perceived within classroom

settings in Dera Ghazi Khan. The findings of the study reveal that various power structures suggested by Michel Foucault can be seen in educational settings, especially his bottom-up approach to power and his idea of power as a circulating force, and can be found everywhere. The respondents support the Foucauldian view, believing power and authority don't stand solely in the hands of teachers; instead, teachers and students both of the respondents believe that power works through interactions and communication within relationships. According to descriptive findings from forty responses, respondents show awareness and acknowledgement of institutional power and behavioural regulation. The study also suggests that more than 80% respondents agreed that various factors influence the overall functioning of power, including teachers' decisions, assessments and classroom management. It also examines how knowledge plays a key role in maintaining power relations within the learning spaces. Overall, the findings support Foucault's theory that power is everywhere, as students also agree with this notion, and they do not see contemporary classrooms as hierarchical places where only teachers hold the power. The findings are consistent with the idea put forward by Michael Foucault and provide initial evidence that his concepts have a significant impact on teachers and students in this particular educational setting. Furthermore, students showcase agency by questioning, resisting or accepting academic norms. The high degree of agreement from both the teachers and students indicates that they believe classroom power is spread through interactions, regulations and institutional practices instead of being exclusively held by teachers and or the state. However, the statistics do not prove the absence of classroom hierarchies; rather, they indicate that participants agreed with certain claims or statements. The descriptive patterns indicate the need for more thorough research while providing the primary support for the applicability of Foucauldian ideas in this context.

8. Suggestion for Future Research

Future research should pay attention to the material practices, including educational institutions, with the spatial arrangement of seating patterns, corridor design, staff-room accessibility with surveillance systems, assessment rubrics, timetables and dress codes. Researchers can also examine the role of technologies such as CCTV cameras, biometric systems, and digital grading platforms in contributing to disciplinary practices.

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